

Cryogel-based Ag⁰/Ag₂O nanocomposites for iodide removal from water

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Abstract

In this study novel silver-modified cryogels were synthesized and applied for the removal of iodide from aqueous solutions. The co-allylamine-methacrylic acid-DMAAm-BisAAM (AAC) and co-allylamine-2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propansulfonic acid-DMAAm-BisAAM (SAC) cryogels were decorated with silver by one-step ion-exchange technique and characterized by TEM/EDS, SEM/EDS, FT-IR, XRD and zeta potential measurements. The silver loading was up to 159 and 98 mg/g for AAC and SAC cryogel nanocomposites, respectively. The silver is found in the structure of cryogels in the form of Ag₂O and Ag⁰ nanoparticles and the formation of metallic silver is attributed to *in situ* reduction of silver by the functional groups of the cryogels. The nanocomposites showed rapid kinetics and high adsorption capacity towards iodide. The equilibrium studies showed that the removal of iodide is higher than the theoretically expected based on the Ag:I molar ratio of 1:1. The analysis of the surface of the cryogels confirmed the theoretical Ag:I molar ratio and a study of the solution phase revealed that small amounts of leached Ag⁺ from the cryogels resulted in the formation of AgI colloids which, under the conditions of the experiments, exhibit Ag:I molar ratios lower than the theoretical value explaining the discrepancies between the theoretical and actual iodide removal rates.

Keywords: cryogels; silver nanoparticles; nanocomposites; iodide removal; water treatment

1. Introduction

Iodine is an essential micronutrient absolutely necessary for the neurological activity and thyroid gland function of human body. Iodine in water exists in iodide (I⁻), triiodide (I₃⁻) and iodate (IO₃⁻) forms, depending on the pH and redox conditions. The presence of iodine in water is mainly due to seawater and does not pose any potential harm for human and environment [1,2]. It is generally used as precursor of iodinated products applied for the disinfection of drinking water [3]. However, under the oxidative conditions used in water treatment plants, iodide can form organic species, which may be a health concern [4]. Nevertheless, organic forms of iodine are not as dangerous as radioactive isotopes of iodine used in uranium fission and as fallout from nuclear weapons testing and accidental by-products of nuclear power plants [5]. Another source of radioactive iodide waste is the medical application of ¹³¹I in the treatment of thyroid cancer [6]. The ¹²⁹I and ¹³¹I radioactive isotopes of iodine might promptly be dissolved in

water and sublimed in air inflicting threats to the environment [7] and due to their prolonged half-life time they may cause long-term negative effect on the human metabolic processes [3,8].

The removal of iodide from water, specially its radioactive forms, has attracted global interest, especially following the accidents in Chernobyl, Ukraine in 1986 with 1.76×10^{18} Bq of iodine ^{131}I discharged and in Fukushima, Japan in 2011 with 1.5×10^{17} Bq of ^{131}I discharged. New approaches are necessary for rapid and efficient removal of iodide as the existing ones such as anion exchange suffer from relatively low selectivity and leaching of secondary anions to the water. An alternative and highly selective method is the use of silver nanoparticles (NPs) which readily react with iodide anions to form insoluble silver iodide (AgI). However, the direct use of pure Ag NPs or another silver compound to precipitate iodine species is impractical firstly because the capacity and adsorption dynamics of the removal mainly depend on the specific surface area of AgNPs [9] and secondly due to the chemistry of AgI in water, as it forms small crystalline agglomerates and colloids, which are difficult to be separated from the solution phase [4]. A way to overcome this disadvantage is to use Ag-modified composite materials and remove iodide via surface reaction. Various types of porous and non-porous adsorbents doped with Ag NPs and its oxides were synthesized for targeted removal of iodide from water and are summarized in Table 1. It is important to notice that in most studies the reported adsorption capacity is a sum of the iodide removed by surface reaction and physical adsorption. An issue in those studies is that the formed AgI was qualitatively confirmed via surface characterization methods such as XRD and EDS but the surface reaction mechanisms and the potential leaching of silver and subsequent formation of colloids has not been thoroughly investigated. Thus, a more detailed qualitative and quantitative examination of the mechanism of removal and proper quantification of adsorbed and leached iodide is required.

Table 1
Ag-modified adsorbent for iodide removal from aqueous phase

Adsorbent	Ag loading (w/w%)	Initial iodide concentration ppm	Adsorption capacity (mg/g)	Reference
Ag@activated carbon	1.05	450	38.1	[10]
AgCl@calcium alginate	10.9	0-700	133	[11]
MIL-101(Cr)-SO ₃ Ag	3.6	920	244	[12]
Ag ₂ O-Ag/TiO ₂	5.8	1150	208	[13]
AgII@MIL101	2	500	43.2	[7]
Ag ₂ O-Ag ₂ O ₃ @ZIF-8	20	600	232	[14]
Ag ₂ O@Mg(OH) ₂	32.3	200	368.6	[15]
Ag ⁺ @silica aerogel	35.5	17000	88	[16]
Ag@carbon aerogel	10	1.27	0.25	[4]
AgCl-SPAC	34.3	1	160	[17]
Ag ₂ O@titanate nanolamina	-	500	428	[5]
Ag ₂ O@sodium niobate nanofibers	-	50-1000	54.5	[18]
<u>Ag⁺@D201 resin</u>	<u>6.8</u>	<u>300</u>	<u>56.1</u>	[19]

Cryogels are polymers with super-hydrophilic macroporous matrices produced at subzero temperatures [20]. As a result of selection of certain monomers, various functional groups such as -OH, -NH₂, -SO₃H, -COOH and -CONH₂ can be anchored on the surface of the cryogel for effective and targeted removal of several substances from water [21–23]. Cryogels can be used as a scaffolds for adsorbent materials or NPs, i.e. forming nanocomposites [23–26]. Cryogels with specific functionalities can be prepared either by directly polymerizing a functional monomer with prepared NPs or by post modifying macroporous scaffold with metal complexes

and through secondary reduction reactions or NPs attachment on the cryogel surface (Berillo et al., 2014; Kurozumi et al., 2015; Lofrano et al., 2016; Loo et al., 2013;). For example, Loo et al [32] synthesized p(SA-MBAm) cryogel from sodium acrylate and N,N-methylenebis(acrylamide), modified it with silver NPs and then used for bactericidal activity towards *Escherichia coli* bacterial culture. All of these NPs-decorated cryogels were used for different purposes such as water disinfection or selective removal of different metal ions from aqueous solutions.

The objective of this research was to investigate the synthesis of two novel cryogel-based silver nanocomposites (AAC and SAC), to study their ability to remove iodide from water and explore the mechanisms involved. The cryogels were made by using different proportions of allylamine, amide based precursors with main difference in key monomer, methacrylic acid for AAC and 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid for SAC. The nanocomposites were characterized using SEM/EDS, TEM/EDS, XRD, FT-IR and zeta potential measurements before and after the interaction with iodide. Equilibrium, and kinetics experiments accompanied with modeling are presented and in combination to surface and aqueous phase characterizations iodide removal mechanisms are proposed. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the use of silver-impregnated cryogels for the removal of iodide from water is for the first time presented in the literature.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

N,N-dimethylacrylamide (DMAAm, 99.0%), allylamine (AA) (98.0 %), H₃PO₄ (85%), N,N-Methylenebis(acrylamide) (BisAAm, 99.0%), methacrylic acid (MAAc)(99.0 %), 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid (AMPS), NaOH, ammonium persulfate (APS, 98.0 %), N,N,N',N'-Tetramethyl ethylene diamine (TEMED, ≥99.5%), AgNO₃ (≥99 %) and KI (≥99.5%) reagents were purchased from Sigma-Algrich (Germany). The water used for the preparation of all solutions was purified using a Puris MR-RO1600 (Mirae ST, South Korea) reverse osmosis unit.

2.2 Synthesis of AAC and SAC cryogels

The AAC and SAC cryogels were synthesized using a standard free-radical polymerisation under cryoconditions. Preliminary experiments were performed to optimize the ratio of monomers, cross-linking agent and initiators. MAAc and AMPS for AAC and SAC cryogels, respectively, BisAAm and NaOH in the amount provided in Table 2 were added into degassed by N₂ gas ultra-pure water and mixed under vigorous stirring to obtain a homogenous solution. In another flask DMAAm, AA and H₃PO₄ were mixed in degassed ultra-pure water. After mixing these two solutions in a glass beaker, TEMED was added and the solution was cooled down to 2-4°C for 30 minutes under nitrogen atmosphere. Finally, 5 wt% of APS was added instantly and 2 ml of the mixture was poured into plastic syringes of diameter of 1 cm. The syringes were plugged at the one end and immersed in -12°C ethanol in a program-controlled refrigerated bath (Julabo F34, Germany) and for 24 hours. The obtained cryogels were thawed at room temperature, washed with 2 L of purified water and freeze-dried in FreeZone 2.5L (Labconco, USA) instrument via lyophilization technique at -52 °C under vacuum (0.4 mbar) for 72 h in order to remove water [33–36]. The yield of gel fraction was 83% and 92% for AAC and SAC cryogel, respectively.

Table 2. Mass and molar composition of 6% initial monomeric mixture for preparation of AAC and SAC cryogels, with 8.8 to 1 and 10 to 1 mol ratio of monomers to cross-linking agent, respectively.

	AAC			SAC		
	Mass/volume	mmol	Monomers mol/mol ratio	Mass/volume	mmol	Monomers mol/mol ratio
BisAAM, g	0.2186	1.41	2	0.1395	1	0.90
MAAc, ml	0.4125	4.8	7	-		
AMPS, g	-			0.5644	3	2.72
DMAAm, g	0.3445	3.47	5	0.372	4.1	3.74
AA, ml	0.300	4.0	5.3	0.200	3	2.67
5M NaOH, ml	1.2			0.42		
H ₃ PO ₄ , ml	0.1373			0.092		
5% APS, ml	0.25			0.25		
TEMED, ml	0.0155			0.0155		
H ₂ O	17.3			17.5		

2.3 Modification of synthesized cryogels

The dry cryogel monoliths with mass 80 mg were incubated in 100 ml of 1.3 mM solution of AgNO₃ for three days under shaking at 100 rpm. After the modification the Ag-cryogels were gently washed with ultra-pure water to remove the unbounded silver nitrate solution from pore structure of cryogel. The washed cryogels were freeze-dried and stored at room temperature in tightly closed containers for further use.

The amount of silver impregnated was calculated using Eq.1 from the difference between the initial and residual concentrations of silver ions analysed by atomic absorption spectrometer AAnalyst 400 (Perkin Elmer, USA):

$$q_{eq} = \frac{C_o - C_f}{m} \times V \quad (1)$$

where q_{eq} is the Ag loading on the material (mg/g), C_o and C_f are silver concentrations (mg/L) in the initial and final solutions, respectively, V the volume of solution (L), and m is the initial weight of the cryogel (g). To avoid confusion, throughout the paper the term “loading” and symbol q (mg/g) is used for the amount of species adsorbed per initial weight of the solid phase (before adsorption) and the term “content” and symbol ct (mg/g) for the amount of species adsorbed per total weight of the solid phase (initial weight plus the weight of the adsorbed species). The former is typically used for kinetics and equilibrium studies while the later for XRF, EDS and other compositional analyses and they are related as follows:

$$ct = \frac{q}{1 + \left(\frac{q}{1000}\right)} \quad (2)$$

Blanks with the same initial concentration of silver and volume without solids were tested and that the Ag⁺ losses due to adsorption on tube walls were less than 2%. All experiments were carried out in duplicate and the average standard error was lower than 2%.

2.4 Leaching of silver from the cryogels

To evaluate the permanency of adsorbed silver on the solids leaching experiments under neutral (pH 7) conditions were conducted. First, the cryogel samples were gently washed with 1L of ultra-pure water to wash out AgNO_3 solution remained in the pores of the materials. The tightly closed containers were left for 10 days with shaking at 120 rpm at room temperature. The samples were withdrawn after 10 d from each container and analysed for leached silver. All the leaching experiments were carried out in duplicate and the average values are reported.

2.5 Characterization of materials

For all characterizations the cryogel samples were dried by lyophilisation technique using the same conditions mentioned above. The macroporous structure of parent, silver contained, and iodide adsorbed cryogels were studied by Zeiss Crossbeam 540 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) at 3 kV, equipped with a backscattered electron detector. An Energy-Dispersive X-ray (EDS) spectrometer (INCA X-sight, Oxford Instruments) connected to SEM was used for determination of elemental composition by spot and area elemental analyses. Infrared spectra of preliminary crushed into a fine powder dry cryogels were recorded for the sum of 32 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} in the range of $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ using Agilent Technologies Cary 600 Series FTIR spectrophotometer equipped with attenuated total reflection (ATR). The zeta potential of cryogels were measured by Zetasizer Nano (Malvern, UK). The crystalline phases of Ag-cryogels before and after iodide adsorption was identified by X-Ray diffractometer (XRD) (Rigaku SmartLab, Japan) with HyPix-3000 high energy resolution 2D HPAD detector, at 40 kV and 40 mA. The investigation of the silver formations on the cryogels was performed via a high-resolution JEOL JEM-1400 transmission electron microscope (TEM), operating at 120 kV. To determine the elemental composition of nanoparticles INCA Energy TEM 350 EDS spectrometer connected to JEOL JEM-2100 TEM operating at 200 kV was used.

2.6 Batch adsorption kinetics and models

A volume of 100 ml of 100 ppm iodide solution was prepared by dissolving analytical grade KI in ultra-pure water without pH adjustment and mixed with 80 mg of cryogels in plastic tubes under shaking at 120 rpm and room temperature. After certain time intervals, aliquots of 50-100 μl were taken, diluted to up to 3 mL and analysed for iodide on UV-Vis spectrophotometer (PhotoLab 6600) at 227 nm wavelength. The total sampling volume was no more than 2% of the initial volume in all experiments. The blank tubes with the same concentration of KI without cryogel were also run and the total adsorption of iodide on tubes walls was less than 1%. Preliminary experiments with KI solutions showed that are stable and no iodide oxidation occurs for at least 21 days in a wide range of concentrations and pH. Also, the solutions after reaching equilibrium with cryogels were scanned in the range of 190-500 nm and no iodine and triiodide were detected.

The pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order models were used for studying the removal mechanism in their linear forms [37,38]:

$$\ln(q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (4)$$

where q_e and q_t is the equilibrium and at time t (min) I⁻ loading, respectively and $k_1(\text{min}^{-1})$ and k_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) are the pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order constants. The constant k_1 and the equilibrium I⁻ loading (q_e^{cal}) can be obtained from the slope and intercept of the linear plot of $\ln(q_e^{\text{exp}} - q_t)$ versus t by use of the experimental data. The values of k_2 and equilibrium and at time t (min) I⁻ loading (q_e^{cal}) can be calculated from the linear fit of t/q_t versus t by use of the experimental data.

2.7 Equilibrium studies

Equilibrium experiments were conducted by contacting cryogel samples of varying mass of 10 to 100 mg with 100 ml of 100 ppm KI solution without pH adjustment under shaking on a Rotamax 120 (Heidolph, Germany) shaker at room temperature until equilibrium was reached. The attainment of equilibrium was monitored by periodical 24h measurements and the total sampling volume was less than 2%. The samples were diluted and analyzed by UV-Vis spectrometer. The pH and conductivity of the solutions were measured by SevenEasy pH and conductivity meters (Mettler Toledo, USA). The experiments were conducted in duplicate and averaged values are reported with a standard error no more than 3%. Finally, the Ag^+ , Na^+ and K^+ concentrations in the solutions were measured by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAnalyst 400, Perkin-Elmer).

2.8 AgI colloids formation studies

The AgI colloids formation experiments were done by adding dropwise 500 ppm solution of AgNO_3 to 500 ppm solution of KI in Ag:I molar ratios from 1:20 to 1:400 under magnetic stirring at 200 rpm. The mixtures were left for 3 days to age and then scanned with UV-Vis spectrophotometer at wavelengths from 190 to 500 nm and analyzed by Zetasizer Nano (Malvern, UK) for determination of sizes and zeta potential of colloids.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Synthesis and modification of cryogels

The Ag loading reached 159 mg/g for AAC and 98 mg/g for SAC corresponding to Ag-modified samples silver content of 137.2 and 89.3 mg/g, respectively. The measured silver loading is in good agreement with the EDS mapping of a large area (100-200 μm) of the Ag-modified materials (Fig. S1, S2 and Table S1). The proposed mechanism of adsorption of silver ions onto cryogels is schematically represented in Fig. 1. The uptake of Ag^+ is attributed to ion exchange with H^+ and Na^+ ions available on the functional groups of cryogels as preliminary experiments showed and also reported elsewhere [5,30,39].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation and photos of the modification of AAC (left) and SAC (right) cryogels

The FT-IR spectra of the parent and Ag-modified samples are presented in Fig. 2. Both parent cryogels have peaks of bounded water and stretching vibration bands of N-H group at approximately 3300 cm^{-1} , and $2930\text{-}2910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to sp^3 hybridized $-\text{CH}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ groups. The peaks at 1616 and 1540 cm^{-1} of AAC and 1619 and 1537 cm^{-1} of SAC cryogel correspond to the primary amide and secondary amide groups, respectively [40,41]. However after the contact with silver ions amide (I) and amide (II) groups are shifted by 10 and 9 cm^{-1} in AAC-Ag and 5 and 4 cm^{-1} in SAC-Ag, respectively, to lower frequencies with reducing of the peaks intensity in comparison with parent sample. This phenomenon can be attributed to deprotonation or metal-binding on carbonyl groups [41]. Also, AAC cryogel contains stretching vibrations bands of a dissociated carboxyl group at 1141 cm^{-1} and non-dissociated carboxylic groups at 1390 cm^{-1} , respectively [40]. In AAC cryogel the bands of a dissociated carboxyl group frequency at 1136 cm^{-1} and non-dissociated carboxylic groups at $1251\text{-}1217\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are shifted for $15\text{-}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at AAC-Ag sample after interaction with silver ions. The presence of 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid in the structure of SAC cryogel gives distinctive peaks of the sulfonic acid; sulfoxide, sulphide and C-S functional groups at 1458 cm^{-1} , 1184 cm^{-1} , 1039 cm^{-1} and 626 cm^{-1} , respectively [42,43]. These functional groups were also involved to the binding of silver ions resulting in shifting of bands by $4\text{-}8\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra of parent, Ag-modified and iodide adsorbed AAC and SAC cryogels

In Fig. 3 the photographs of cryogels are presented whose color varies by time. Depending on the synthesis conditions, silver nanoparticles have different sizes and shapes, which give them different optical properties detected at a wavelength of 400 to 750 nm [44–48]. Huang and Hu synthesized citrate-stabilized free Ag° NPs with further reduction by different amount of NaBH_4 in the aqueous solutions to demonstrate dependence of colour of colloidal silver nanoparticles to the size and shape of nanoparticles [48]. In our study, as it is discussed below, the functional groups of cryogels participated not only in ion exchange and chelation of silver ions, but in the reduction of silver ions to metallic silver nanoparticles which led to change the colour. Comparing these colors in Fig. 3 with the those of Huang and Xu the dark red color of AAC cryogel indicates the presence of spherical and rod-shaped Ag° NPs with a size up to 25 nm and the yellow color of SAC cryogel indicates the formation of spherical silver nanoparticles with an average diameter of 5 nm [48]. However, these are only indications and XRD along with TEM characterizations are needed, which are presented below followed by a discussion on the mechanism of silver reduction of silver on the cryogels.

Fig. 3. Color of AAC and SAC cryogels during the Ag adsorption at various times

Representative TEM micrographs are shown in Fig. 4(A,B) and are in general agreement with the aforementioned sizes of silver NPs. Based on a number of TEM analyses it was observed that most NPs in AAC-Ag are in the range of 20-50 nm while SAC-Ag shows considerably lower particles in the range of 3-20 nm. The larger NPs size of AAC can be attributed to the higher amount of impregnated silver possibly leading to aggregation of silver particles to form clusters which is stabilized by nitrogen-containing groups in polymer structure [49]. According to TEM images both Ag-modified cryogels have well dispersed NPs with low degree of agglomeration. The uniform dispersion may be attributed to equable complexation with functional groups which steadily form polymer network of cryogels. Representative point TEM/EDS analysis are shown in Fig. 4 C,D show that there is no oxygen and thus these NPs are Ag°. However, in other EDS analyses (not shown here) the oxygen in some NPs reaches 19% in AAC-Ag and 17% in SAC-Ag and thus Ag₂O NPs coexist on the surface.

Fig. 4. TEM/EDS images and composition of AAC-Ag (A,C) and SAC-Ag (B,D) cryogels

XRD corroborates the conclusions presented above as the spectra of AAC-Ag cryogel before adsorption of iodide show characteristic peaks of Ag°NPs at 38.29°, 44.62°, and 77.85°

and also peaks of Ag₂O NPs at 32.39° and 65.16°, while SAC-Ag sample has peaks of Ag° NPs at 38.30°, 44.51° and of Ag₂O NPs at 32.50° and 64.85° as shown in Fig. 5. After interaction with iodide, many characteristic diffraction peaks of AgI at 2θ 23.71°, 39.13°, 46.31° can be observed for both cryogel nanocomposites, while the diffraction peaks attributed to Ag° NPs and Ag₂O NPs disappear. These observations show that the I⁻ removal occurs according to the following reactions with the involvement of dissolved oxygen (Tauanov and Inglezakis, 2019):

Fig. 5. XRD spectrum of silver modified and iodide loaded AAC (A) and SAC (B) cryogels

The presence of diffraction peaks of Ag° NPs confirms the *in situ* reduction of silver. The reduction reaction without application of additional reducing agent is related to high oxidative properties of silver ions due to standard redox potential of +0.75V [50]. Previously such phenomenon of self-reduction upon moderate heating or presence of light was described for chitosan-[AuCl₄] based cryogels [31,51]. Amino group redox potential is similar to ammonia, which is approximately -0.27 V [52]. Thus, the reduction of Ag⁺ to Ag° could be explained by redox potential of amino group [53]. Finally, from the SEM/EDS analysis is evident that after the interaction with silver the structure of cryogels is still intact with uniform distribution of silver (Fig. S1,S2). After interaction with iodide the surface of cryogels was covered by iodide ions forming the AgI with congruent yellow color.

3.2. Adsorption kinetics

The iodide removal kinetics are shown in Fig. 5. Taking into account the small amount of cryogels used (80 mg) the kinetics are very fast and in the first 0.5h AAC-Ag and SAC-Ag samples removed up to 35% of iodide and equilibrium is reached after 30h when removal reached 93% for AAC-Ag cryogel and 77% for SAC-Ag cryogel. Parent AAC and SAC cryogels did not adsorb iodide which can be attributed to the hindrance of protonated aminogroup with counter ion hydro or dihydrophosphate (RCH₂-NH₃⁺H₂PO₄⁻).

Fig. 5. Removal kinetics of iodide from aqueous (80 mg of cryogel in 100 ml of solution)

Fig. 6. The pseudo-first-order (A) and pseudo-second-order (B) model plots for the adsorption of iodide on the AAC-Ag and SAC-Ag cryogels

The fitting of the pseudo-first and pseudo-second order models on the experimental data (Fig.6) was evaluated and the derived parameters are given in Table 3. The fitting quality is similar for both models but the calculated solid phase loadings (q_e^{cal}) predicted by the pseudo-second order model are closer to experimental ones (q_e^{exp}). Therefore, it could be concluded that the pseudo-second order model better describes Γ adsorption kinetics for both Ag-modified cryogels indicating a chemical sorption process [37], which is in agreement with other results of iodide removal by use of silver-impregnated zeolitic imidazolate framework composite [14].

Table 3. Parameters of kinetic models for iodide sorption by cryogels

Pseudo-first order				
	q_e^{exp} (mg/g)	q_e^{cal} (mg/g)	K_1 (min^{-1})	R^2
AAC-AgI	117.2	87.3	0.1834	0.9686
SAC-AgI	96.8	61.6	0.2293	0.9834
Pseudo-second order				
	q_e^{exp} (mg/g)	q_e^{cal} (mg/g)	K_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	R^2
AAC-AgI	117.2	97.1	0.0103	0.9713
SAC-AgI	96.8	86.9	0.008	0.9765

After adsorption of iodide the color of both nanocomposites turns to yellow (Fig. 8A,C), due to the formation of AgI [15]. The presence of AgI on the surface of cryogels was investigated SEM which show the surface coated with the precipitate and EDS technique which shows the iodide dispersed on the surface of the cryogels (Fig. 8 B,D and Figs. S3 and S4). Also, the AgI formations can be seen in the high resolution TEM image (Fig. 9). As expected, the size of nanoparticles after uptake of I is slightly larger than the initial NPs (Fig. 4), which is consistent with the previous findings of Yang et al. [54] and Mu et al. [18]. TEM shows dark areas which are probably agglomerated silver and AgI NPs.

Fig 8. Photographs and SEM images of AAC-Ag (A,B) and SAC-Ag (C,D) after adsorption of iodide

Fig. 9. TEM of AAC-AgI (A,B) and SAC-AgI (C,D)

3.3 Equilibrium adsorption isotherms

The equilibrium results are shown in Fig. 10. The isotherms shapes are sigmoidal and the maximum loading was 326 mg/g for the Ag-AAC and 247 mg/g for the Ag-SAC.

Fig. 10. Isotherms of iodide removal by cryogels

Based on the silver content of the Ag-modified samples the theoretical iodide loadings of the solid phase are 161.4 mg/g and 105 mg/g for AAC and SAC, respectively, considerably higher than the measured iodide equilibrium loadings (Fig. 10). This is confirmed by the EDS mapping of a large area (50-100 μm) of the materials showing that Ag and I are uniformly distributed on the cryogels surface with Ag:I molar ratios close to 1 (Fig. S3, S4). The silver and iodide content measured by EDS are in excellent agreement with the expected silver and iodide content of the iodide-loaded cryogels (Table S1). Also, the discrepancy between the theoretical and actual iodide loading is increasing by decreasing the mass of cryogel to solution volume ratio.

Such discrepancies were also observed by Mao et al [7] for the removal of iodide by Ag@MIL-101 composite. The authors presented the following mechanism:

According to these reactions, first Ag^+ is released from the composite and reacts with I^- to yield AgI with simultaneous oxidation of I^- to I_2 . Subsequently, the generated I_2 can be adsorbed by the nearby AgI nanoparticles released from the surface of material to form AgI_3 , or be adsorbed by complex ions (AgI_{2n-1}) to form more stable complex ions (AgI_{2n+1}). However, no data verified the existence of I_2 except the large adsorption capacity and thus their explanation is incomplete. The same discrepancy between experimental and theoretical iodide loading were observed in the study of Zhao et al [12]. They synthesized MIL-101(Cr)- SO_3H metal-organic framework sample

modified by Ag^+ with maximum loading of silver 35.8 mg/g. After interaction with NaI the parent MIL-101(Cr)- SO_3H iodide loading was 94.1 mg/g and this of Ag-modified sample 244.2 mg/g. The difference of almost 150 mg/g between the materials was not explained by the authors although they authors mentioned some release of silver from the material without any further analysis.

To better understand these observations, the release of Ag^+ and Na^+ from the cryogels and the removal of K^+ from the solutions was studied and the results are presented in Fig. 12. As it can be seen, although there is no trend there is Ag^+ some release from the cryogels and its concentration in the solution is between 1.3-8 ppm, similar to the concentration of the released Na^+ which is between 2.6-7.8 ppm. Taking into account that leaching experiments in pure water showed negligible release of silver from the Ag-modified cryogels (0.05-0.54%) the release of Ag^+ and possibly Na^+ can be attributed to ion exchange with H^+ and K^+ from the solution. Indeed, as is shown in Fig. 11 the K^+ concentration in the solution is between 5.8-24.5 ppm, lower than its initial concentration of 31.7 ppm. The slow release of Ag^+ in an iodide-rich solution can lead to the formation of colloidal AgI that have lower Ag:I molar ratio than 1 as the theory predicts [55,56]. As it was experimentally confirmed by measurements in the model solutions by use of UV-Vis and ion chromatography, AgI colloids are detected by UV-Vis (Fig 13) but the bounded iodide cannot be measured by UV-Vis or ion chromatography and this explains the discrepancy observed in the equilibrium results. More discussion on this is conducted in the next paragraph.

Fig. 11. Release of Ag⁺ and Na⁺ from the cryogels and K⁺ remaining in the solution under different cryogel/solution volume ratio.

After interaction with Ag-modified cryogels the pH and conductivity of the solutions change (Table S2). The conductivity of solution decreases from 104.4 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 29.35- 88.65 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for AAC-Ag experiments and to 13.3-96.9 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for SAC-Ag experiments depending on the mass of cryogels mainly due to the removal of I⁻ form the solution. The pH of solutions containing AAC-AgI cryogels increase from 5.56 to 6.11-7.11 probably due to the exchange of H⁺ from the solution for Na⁺ from the cryogels and the dissolution reaction of Ag₂O to Ag⁺ (equation 6). On the contrary, the pH in SAC-AgI containing solutions remains slightly acidic around the initial pH of 5.59 which is probably due to the H⁺ release from the sulfonic acid groups.

3.4 AgI colloids formation studies

In the early works of the Verwey and Oberbeek [55,57] the theory of formation and stability of lyophobic colloids are described in detail. An electric double layer is formed around the AgI particles with different charges depending on the relative concentrations I^- and Ag^+ in the solution. If silver nitrate is added to a solution of excess of potassium iodine the formed AgI particles first attract negatively charged iodide anions (Fig. 12) to form potential-forming layer. To this layer the positively charged potassium (K^+) and negatively charged iodide (I^-) ions join to form the ion diffusion layer of counter ions.

Fig. 12. Formation of AgI colloids in excess of iodide

To further investigate the formation of colloids 500 ppm of $AgNO_3$ solution was added dropwise to 500 ppm KI solution resulting in solution Ag:I ratios from 1:20 to 1:400. The solutions were scanned by using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer and the peak at 424-431 nm was observed and attributed to AgI colloids [58]. The same peak was found in the iodide equilibrium solutions after interaction with the Ag-cryogels (Fig.13).

Fig. 13. UV-Vis plot determination of AgI formation

The results of zeta potential measurements and size of colloid solutions presented in Table 5 and confirm the formation of negatively charged particles of colloidal dimensions. With increasing of Ag:I ratio the zeta potential of solutions decreases with increase of size of colloidal AgI. The

zeta potential of AgI colloidal solution decreased from -65.2 mV at the ratio 1:20 of Ag:I to -50.3 mV at 1:400 ratio, in general agreement with the findings of other studies [59]. The sizes of colloid particles linearly increase from 193.9 to 317 nm when the ratio of Ag:I increases from 20 to 400. This phenomenon is observed with very dilute electrolytic solutions in which the colloidal particle size can reach 1000 nm due to an increase in the diffusion layer of the particle [55]. For comparison, the zeta potential of solutions contained 10 mg of AAC-AgI and SAC-AgI samples were -45.1 and -50.9 mV and the average size of the formed colloids 171.4 and 175.7 nm, respectively. Taking into account that colloids formation is a dynamic process and depends on many factors the results are satisfactory and confirm the formation of colloids. This offers a reasonable explanation of the discrepancies between theoretical and actual iodide loading values as the colloids exhibit Ag:I ratios lower than 1.

Table 5. The results of zeta potential and size measurements of AgI colloid solutions

Ag:I molar ratio	Zeta potential (mV)	Average size (nm)
1:20	-65.2 ± 1.0	193±10
1:40	-61.8 ± 2.6	217±9
1:80	-67.1±2.1	212±12
1:80	-66.6±3.2	265±16
1:160	-51.8±2.1	275±14
1:200	-51.2±0.8	264±11
1:240	-52.4±1.9	291±7
1:380	-56.1±2.0	297±14
1:320	-52.4±1.2	307±11
1:360	-52.7±3.1	294±5
1:400	-50.3±2.6	317±21
KI	-0.11±0.03	0

4. Conclusions

In this work, two novel Ag⁰/Ag₂O nanocomposite cryogels were synthesized, characterized and used for the removal of iodide from water. The AAC and SAC cryogels reached a silver loading of 159 and 98 mg/g, respectively. The results showed that amide-induced Ag⁺ reduction takes place on the surface resulting in the formation of Ag⁰ while agglomeration and oxidation result in the formation of Ag₂O nanoparticles. This hypothesis is supported by the colors of the cryogels, FTIR, SEM/EDS and TEM/EDS measurements. In the KI solutions Ag⁰ is oxidized to Ag₂O and then dissolution follows to form Ag⁺ which reacts with I⁻ to form insoluble AgI on the surface of the Ag-cryogels. Ion exchange also takes place between Ag⁺ and Na⁺ from the cryogels and K⁺ and H⁺ from the solution. The removal of I⁻ is fast and follows the pseudo-second order model. Finally, a small release of Ag⁺ during I⁻ removal resulted in the formation of negatively charged AgI colloids in the solution. The Ag:I molar ratios of these colloids is considerably lower than 1 resulting in higher than theoretically expected removal of I⁻ by considering the formation of AgI bulk precipitate. The formation of colloids in the solution provide a satisfactory explanation for other similar discrepancies between observed and theoretically expected I⁻ removals in the literature.

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